

WORLD EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE LEVEL OF MEDIA LITERACY

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Abstract. *Media literacy is a set of skills that enable people to analyze, evaluate, and create different media forms and messages. A person with high media literacy will be able to easily notice which source is reliable and which source is spreading false news. In other words, media literacy is the ability to apply critical thinking skills to the messages and symbols conveyed through the media. Media and information literacy is a set of knowledge, skills, attitudes, skills and practices that enable the effective acquisition, analysis, critical evaluation, interpretation, use, creation and dissemination of information and media products using all necessary tools in creative activities. Today, the ability to select and correctly evaluate information remains relevant in the world mass media.*

Keywords: *media literacy, information literacy, mass media, media literacy.*

МИРОВОЙ ОПЫТ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ УРОВНЯ МЕДИАГРАМОТНОСТИ

Аннотация. *Медиаграмотность — это набор навыков, которые позволяют людям анализировать, оценивать и создавать различные медиаформы и сообщения. Человек с высокой медиаграмотностью сможет легко заметить, какой источник является достоверным, а какой распространяет ложные новости. Другими словами, медиаграмотность — это способность применять навыки критического мышления к сообщениям и символам, передаваемым через средства массовой информации. Медийно-информационная грамотность — это совокупность знаний, умений, установок, умений и практик, позволяющих эффективно приобретать, анализировать, критически оценивать, интерпретировать, использовать, создавать и распространять информацию и медиапродукты с использованием всех необходимых инструментов в творческой деятельности. Сегодня умение отбирать и правильно оценивать информацию остается актуальным в мировых СМИ.*

Ключевые слова: *медиаграмотность, информационная грамотность, средства массовой информации, медиаграмотность.*

INTRODUCTION

In 2015, every American sat on the Internet for 8.4 hours a day and read media content, while Filipinos spend 10.6 hours, Russians spend 4.6 hours, and our country spends 1.6 hours. According to the latest data, the number of Internet users in the world is 2.6 billion, while in Uzbekistan this number has exceeded 19 million, and 7 million of them are mobile users.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

These numbers, which change every month, have made it necessary to separate the necessary information from the unnecessary, to acquire literacy through the media. So what is media literacy? Why is it increasingly important today? In recent years, the multifold acceleration of the flow of information, the increase of positive information as well as negative information has made it necessary to have media literacy. Traditionally, media literacy consisted of a person's ability to analyze literary works and create quality texts. Today, media literacy means knowing why and for what information is being transmitted. Who created this information for a media literate person and for what purpose? Is this message necessary for me?

he should be able to ask the question and draw a correct conclusion, should be critical about it. These questions should be asked not only when you are watching TV with your family, listening to the radio in the car or watching the news on the Internet, but also when you are receiving and evaluating any information. Media literacy is important in understanding today's news environment.

So, why is media literacy necessary? First of all:

1. To understand the essence of the reforms implemented as a full-fledged, active citizen of our legal democratic society;
2. Formation of skills for sorting daily information transmitted and received through mass media;
3. To avoid controlling the human mind through information and to make the right decision in any situation;
4. To be able to analyze positive or negative changes of a person under the influence of visual images and to be able to "read" invisible information given under visual messages;
5. Analyzing the nature of text communications given through mass media;
6. It is necessary to find answers to the questions of where, by whom and for what purposes the information is being transmitted, whose interests it reflects.

RESULTS

There are different opinions about the concept of media literacy, and according to the American International Encyclopedia of Society, it is noted that "media literacy" means being active and literate while feeling the responsibility as a citizen in society, being able to receive and create media texts, it means to be able to analyze and evaluate, to be able to understand the socio-cultural and political content of modern media.

According to S. Firestone, professor of the Royal University of London, media literacy is a movement whose main task is to encourage people to understand, create and evaluate the cultural significance of audiovisual and printed texts.

English political scientist R. Kibey understands media literacy as the transmission of information in various forms, their analysis and evaluation. M. Guetterz says that multimedia literacy includes knowing languages aimed at creating multimedia documents, being able to use devices and methods for information processing, knowing and evaluating new multimedia technologies, and critically accepting media texts.

In our opinion, media literacy is a critical view of all the information transmitted through mass media, an unbiased approach to them, and a conscious approach to sorting each transmitted information.

The goal of media literacy is to understand the priorities and shortcomings of each media, to be able to sort out the information distributed by them and to form the skills to accept the necessary, while the main task is to limit it, realizing the manipulative power of any information consumed by people. It is also to help people understand the role of media and citizen journalism.

According to renowned Indian photojournalist Pabak Sarkar, the first step towards media literacy is being able to ask the right questions. Today, information attacks carried out over the Internet have become part of the national security strategy of every country in the world, and it has been named cyber security. After all, the merging of the virtual and real world, the misunderstanding of the real world by young people through the virtual world, the dissemination

of information that appears positive at first glance, but has a negative effect on the human mind, by various negative forces and currents. It is no secret that it is increasing. There are increasing opinions that it is necessary to make the population media literate in order to prevent these negative aspects affecting the life of the society. Today, media literacy is taught as a separate subject in the complex of humanities in Great Britain and Australia, while in Finland it was included in the curricula of secondary schools in 1970, and in higher education institutions in 1977. In the 1990s, media literacy in the country was replaced by the concept of media education. In Sweden, it has been taught as a separate subject in educational institutions since 1980. In the 1990s, there were attempts to conduct scientific research of media education in Russia, and the researches of O. Baranov, S. Penzin, A. Fyodorov, A. Sharikova and others can be an example of this. In 2002, a course on media education was opened for higher educational institutions of pedagogy. In 2005, the textbook "Media education" was created under the auspices of UNESCO, and the website of film education and media pedagogy was launched in Russia.

Today, no one denies the power of manipulative influence of the information distributed through mass media. If we look at history, it can be seen that the belief in the truth of the news spread through mass media appeared with the appearance of the first newspapers. On November 9, 1874, New York Herald reporter T. B. Connery reported that predators had escaped from Central Park Zoo, and "about two hundred people were injured and trampled, and sixty people were in serious condition. three of them may not arrive until morning. twelve monsters are still at large. it is not yet known where they approached" and at the end of it it was written that the subscribers of the newspaper should not be alarmed, that all this was fabricated. but most of the news did not reach this point, they went to hide, and some even took weapons and went out to kill the predators. In 1939, when CBS radio station Orsona Welles broadcast a radio adaptation of Herbert Wells' War of the Worlds at the Mercury Theater, riots broke out. according to the plot of the novel, Martians invade Earth and poison millions of people with gas. many people tried to escape and hide from the "enemies" from the moment they heard the first part of the radio program. In 1835, the first American tabloid, the New York Sun, published a false report by the journalist Richard Adame Locke that an English astronomer had seen intelligent creatures on the surface of the moon through a telescope. as a result, the newspaper's circulation reached the highest level at that time - 19,000 copies. even the Christian women's society hesitates to fly to the moon to convert them to Christianity.

DISCUSSION

Today, the influence of OAV is no less than it was then. Young people in different parts of the world are committing crimes due to not analyzing the information and accepting it as it is, and those who feel like the heroes of the movie take up weapons and take the lives of innocent people, repeating the actions of "heroes". they are getting ready. for example, after the TV series "Jumong" aired on the TV channels of our republic, young children feel like "jumong" and start fighting with a "sword" in their hands, schoolchildren who have seen war movies and computer games in the USA there are more and more reports of them shooting classmates and innocent people on the street with real guns. Today, terrorist groups calling for Jihad on the Internet and containing the promise of "paradise" have a negative impact on the minds of young people. therefore, prevention of these situations, a conscious approach to information is the need of the hour.

Although the concepts entering our language as a result of media analysis, i.e., media literacy, media education, media studies, etc., are related to each other, scientists are trying to distinguish them from each other in essence. In our opinion, media literacy is an integral part of media education. At the same time, its appearances are increasing. Today, the concepts of media education, media studies, and media culture are used together with the concept of media literacy in receiving, sorting, analyzing, and evaluating media information. Are they different?

media education:

- integrated, interdisciplinary study of media in the educational program;
- a critical approach to the media through practical work and analysis;
- to analyze the "media subject" within a specific discipline;
- to study its form, technologies, methods of information transmission;
- to study media agencies, their social, political and cultural role;
- research activities;
- the student's work with media;
- studies the impact of the media on the audience through language and art.

media studies, in turn:

- theoretical study of media;
- comparative analysis of the media;
- its conceptual structure;
- analysis of media text and the method of its creation;
- interdependence of mass communication, cinematography and cultural sciences;
- studies the interaction of world mass media.

Media literacy is the study of media, based on the following results of media education and aimed at:

- understanding the impact of media on individuals and society;
- understanding of mass communication process;
- ability to understand and analyze media texts;
- understanding the media context;
- creation of media texts and their analysis;
- sets the tasks of evaluating media texts and sorting them.

CONCLUSIONS

Today, the media, i.e., mass media, cinema, theater, types of art, cultural exchanges, any information transmitted through the Internet has a certain effect on the human mind and changes its worldview. It is causing change. The main purpose of the application of the above-mentioned concepts and the pursuit of media education, media literacy, media criticism and media studies today is the creation of information, understanding the process of its dissemination, commercial, political, economic, spiritual and cultural purposes. It is to be able to evaluate the information being disseminated while understanding its essence.

At the moment, it is necessary to include the basics of media education in the curriculum of every educational institution, to explain its basics to children in the form of interactive, various games during preschool education, to choose what is needed by the growing generation in the intense flow of information and to approach it critically. It allows to evaluate without.

This, in turn, is the basis for further strengthening of the citizenship position of young people in the future, for them to be able to objectively assess the events taking place in the world and make the right decisions.

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